

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF PROCESS QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY

Author(s)*: Aurel Mihail ȚÎȚU ^{1,2}, Gheorghe Ioan POP ³
Position: Professor ^{1,2}, PhD Student ³
Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu
Victoriei Street no. 10, code 550024, Sibiu, România ¹
The Academy of Romanian Scientists
54, Splaiul Independenței, Sector 5, Bucharest, Romania ²
University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest
Splaiul Independenței 313, București 060042 ³
Email: mihail.titu@ulbsibiu.ro ^{1,2}, popghitza@gmail.com ³

Abstract

Purpose – *The scientific paper addresses in its own way the specific aspects of process quality management in an organization in the aerospace industry by first streamlining the quality of products and services offered.*

Methodology/approach – *The research methodology was a standard methodology where the life cycle of the management processes is insisted on, as well as the improvement of the management processes in a concrete way in order to increase and achieve the proposed goals. The optimal results in order to significantly reduce the non-conformities are foreshadowed in order to improve the quality management system and subsequently of the integrated quality management system.*

Findings – *The total quality and the zero defects strategy can be correlated with the continuous improvement in order to increase the quality of products and services in the specific water industry that the authors chose to analyze. The aerospace field is a spearhead in terms of current spectrum worldwide. The process approach through a specific method of continuous improvement can lead to an important benefit in terms of management quality, product quality, efficiency and effectiveness and then the market position of the organization.*

Research limitations/implications – *The presented research deals with the issue of improving the quality of process management in a specific industry organization. Planning and making decisions in order to implement efficient management correlated with a good manufacturing organization can lead to increased efficiency and high efficiency.*

Practical implications – *It presents its own point of view on how the efficiency and effectiveness of the processes can be estimated in order to improve the quality of the products promoted on the profile market.*

Originality/value – *All the above have led to a scientific research based primarily on rigorous documentation, on an important qualitative contribution to the efficiency of manufacturing and management itself within an industrial organization in the aerospace field. The processes within the analysis were carefully selected and led to a modeling made so that in the end the authors managed to present solutions to improve the quality of process management and reduce non-conformities in the specific industry.*

Key words: *quality and quality management, process management, aerospace industry.*

Introduction

Akhil Kumar (Kumar, 2018) in his paper, defines the process as a vital element of an organization.

Michael Hammer and James Champy (Hammer and Champy, 1993) and (Buhl, Roglinger, Stockl, and Braunwarth, 2015) argued in the early 1990s that by redesigning business processes, organizations could achieve major productivity improvements. These improvements represent faster deliveries to customers in business - shorter order-to-cash cycles and labor savings needed to work in processes.

Many organizations do not yet have formal processes for how things are done. People need to "know" how things are done and follow the routine.

However, unless a description of the process is explicitly noted, it is not possible to analyze this description, nor to identify inefficiencies or even make improvements.

Many organizations have continued to perform unnecessary tasks for decades, but without analyzing their purpose. In these cases there is a risk that additional copies of a document will be sent to more people than necessary, and therefore additional approvals are required. When a person in an organization is asked why he or she is doing this, the answer he or she will receive will be "I've always done that." Is this due to organizational inertia, and often no one has thought about why things are done the way they are done?

In other words, Akhil Kumar, Rosemann (2006), Rotaru (2011) and Sedera (2004) state that:

- a process is a way of carrying out activities to achieve a goal;
- a process model is a formal representation of a series of related activities that are carried out in a specific order to achieve a clear objective;
- a business process is a collection of activities that require one or more types of inputs and create an output that has value for the customer;
- a business process is defined as a chain of activities whose ultimate goal is the production of a specific product for a particular customer or market.

Figure 1. Defining the process

Management processes. General information about processes in the aeronautical industry

Dumas and his collaborators proposed six stages of the life cycle of management processes (Dumas, La Rosa, Mendling, and Reijers, 2013), (Dijkman, Vanderfeesten, and Reijers, 2011):

- process identification;
- process discovery;
- process analysis;
- process redesign;

- implementation of processes;
- process monitoring and control.

Figure 2. Stages of the life cycle of management processes

Leadership functions are a systematic way of doing things. Management is a process that highlights the fact that all managers, regardless of their aptitude or ability, engage in some interconnected functions to achieve their desired goals.

Planning, organization, coordination and control are the 4 functions of management, which function as a continuous process. In the planning phase, managers must establish a plan, then organize resources according to the plan, then coordinate employees to work according to the plan and finally control everything by monitoring and measuring the effectiveness of the plan.

The basic activities of the management process. Own interpretations

The management process / functions involve 4 basic activities. These are (www.iedunote.com, 2020):

- Planning and decision making - determining actions;
- Organization - coordination of activities and resources;
- Leadership - managing, motivating and guiding people;
- Control - monitoring and evaluation activities.

Planning and decision making - determining the course of action

Looking ahead and anticipating possible trends or events that could influence the work is of major importance, similar to the manager's position.

Planning involves setting the goal of an organization and deciding how best to accomplish it. Planning involves making decisions about goals and setting the course of future actions from a set of alternatives to achieving goals.

The plan facilitates the maintenance of managerial effectiveness, as it functions as a guide for future activities dedicated to staff. The selection of objectives, as well as the ways to achieve them is what planning entails.

Planning involves selecting missions and objectives as well as actions to achieve them. Planning requires making decisions or choosing future courses of action from alternatives.

In short, planning means determining what the organization's position is and what the situation should be at some point in the future and deciding how best to make it happen.

Planning helps maintain managerial effectiveness by guiding future activities.

For a manager, planning and decision making requires the ability to predict, visualize, and deliberate anticipation.

Organization - coordination of activities and resources

Organization can be defined as the process by which established plans are close to realization. Once a manager sets his goals and develops his plans, his next managerial function is to organize human resources and other resources identified as necessary by the plan to achieve the goal. The organization involves determining how activities and resources should be combined and coordinated.

The organization can also be defined as a structure intentionally formalized by positions or roles for people to complete an organization.

The organization produces a structure of relationships in an organization and through these structured relationships the plans are followed.

Indeed, organization is that part of management that involves: establishing an intentional role structure for people to complete the organization. Intentionally, to ensure that all the tasks necessary to achieve the objectives are assigned to those who can do their best.

The purpose of an organizational structure is to create an environment for the best human performance. The structure must define the task to be performed. The rules thus established must also be designed according to the abilities and motivations of the people available.

The staff is related to the organization and involves filling and maintaining busy positions in the structure of the organization.

This can be done by determining the positions to be filled, identifying the workforce requirement, filling vacancies and training employees so that the assigned tasks can be performed effectively and efficiently.

Managerial functions of promotion, demotion, dismissal, transfer, etc. they are also included in the broad task of "staff (human resources)". The staff ensures that the right person is placed in the correct position.

The organization assumes where exactly the decisions will be made, who will work and what tasks it will have to perform, for whom and how the resources will be gathered.

Leadership - Managing, motivating and guiding people

The third basic managerial function is Leadership, which involves having the ability to influence people for a certain purpose or for a certain reason. Leadership is considered to be the most important and challenging of all managerial activities.

Leadership influences or determines the human resource in the organization to work in its interest.

Leadership involves creating a positive attitude of the organization's members towards work and the organization's objectives. It is necessary because it helps to achieve the objectives in an effective and efficient way by changing the behavior of the employees.

Leadership is key to leadership. Most authors do not consider coordination as a separate function of management. Rather, it considers coordination to be the essence of leadership for achieving harmony between individual efforts to achieve group goals.

Motivation is an essential quality for a leader. Motivation is the function of the management process to influence people's behavior based on knowing the cause and the channels that support human behavior in a certain direction.

Effective managers must be effective leaders.

Because leadership involves fellowship, and people tend to follow those who clearly provide a means of meeting their own needs, hopes, and aspirations, leadership involves styles of approaches, communication, and motivational leadership.

Control - Monitoring and evaluation of activities

Monitoring organizational progress toward meeting goals is called control. Monitoring progress is essential to ensure that organizational goals are met.

Control means measuring, comparing, finding deviations and correcting organizational activities performed to achieve the goal or objectives. Control consists of activities such as: measuring performance, comparing with the existing standard and finding and correcting deviations.

Control activities are generally concerned with measuring the achievements and results of actions taken to achieve the goal.

Some means of control, such as the budget for expenditure, the record of inspections and the recording of lost working hours, are generally familiar. Each means of control also shows whether the plans are being met.

If deviations persist, correction is indicated. Whenever the results differ from the planned action, the responsible persons must be identified and the necessary measures taken to improve performance.

Thus, the results are pursued by controlling what people do. Control as a function of the management process, even if it is the last, does not mean that it is the least important.

The statement "planning without control is useless" is as correct as possible. In short, we can say that the control function allows the fulfillment of the plan.

All the functions of the management process are interconnected and cannot be ignored.

The management process designs and maintains an environment in which staff, working together in groups, meet selected objectives effectively.

Manufacturing subprocess of structural components in the aeronautical industry

The manufacturing thread brings direct value to the organization. In the organization chosen for the research project, the manufacturing processes represent the complete technological flow of manufacturing the structural components.

Manufacturing processes require direct or indirect control. In the aeronautical industry, manufacturing processes are controlled by major aircraft manufacturers, by defining manufacturing process and inspection standards that suppliers must comply with in the technological component manufacturing process.

Figure 3. Manufacturing processes in the industrial organization

These process and inspection standards are called: process specifications and have the role of establishing for all suppliers in the field, the same manufacturing process parameters as well as their limits. In this way, they manage to design and plan the manufacturing process for the entire supply chain, in order to obtain quality products. The control of process parameters, through various methods, is a direct control of the manufacturing process. In other words, the values of the parameters resulting from the process within the predetermined limits are followed directly.

Process control can also be performed indirectly by following certain characteristics of the products, resulting from the analyzed process.

Figure 4. Technological process of achieving structural landmarks in the aeronautical industry (www.universalalloy.com, 2020)

In the field of aeronautics, certain manufacturing or inspection processes have a more special character being considered processes with a major impact on products. Reason why aircraft manufacturers are involved in qualifying suppliers by conducting qualification audits and process evaluation

Thus, it is considered as special processes, processes of realization of materials / semi-finished products, processes of heat treatments and inspection of materials / semi-finished products, certain processes of mechanical processing, chemical processes of surface treatment, non-destructive inspections, assembly processes and inspection of assembly elements.

It is considered that the control of products (Figure 5) can be performed similarly to that of processes, directly or indirectly. The direct control of the product is performed by comparing the designed requirements with values or attributes measured directly on the product. Indirect control arises from the control of process parameters applied to the product in question

Figure 5. Direct or indirect control of the product

The process of controlling the resulting non-conformities is critical, and is applied at all hierarchical levels, due to the impact they can have. Impact in terms of safety, which is critical in aeronautics and of course costs. Thus, most organizations in the field of aeronautics have policies for managing non-compliant products under special conditions by their very clear identification and segregation from products in production. Also, products declared scrap are destroyed immediately.

The aeronautical field, as it is also covered in the media, is based on large chains of suppliers and their control. For these reasons, the supplier control process is a process of very high importance being a process audited by each certification authority.

The importance of controlling the requirements and their interpretation is generated by the fact that at the end of the aircraft manufacturing process, each structure made by different suppliers must fit.

In the aeronautical industry, the supplier control process is focused on:

- Control of requirements to the supplier, both product and process;
- Process control and process qualification at suppliers:
- Control of products made by suppliers:
- Control of product documentation.

All these processes are audited and certified by both certification authorities and major aircraft manufacturers.

Figure 6. Distribution of A350 Airbus aircraft structure suppliers worldwide (www.westworldconsulting.com, 2020)

Conclusions

All the input elements in the process are transformed, within an “N” process, by carrying out coordinated activities in relation to a management thinking, resulting in output elements with added value. Each influencing factor has a greater or lesser impact on the outputs.

Each process within the organization has an efficiency calculated in relation to the quality and quantity of outputs from that process, without taking into account the quality and quantity of information at the entry into the process.

The influence of management activities (M-Figure 7) within the processes is achieved by organizing the activities within the processes, using procedures and work instructions (P-Figure 7).

Figure 7. Influencing factors in a process

These instructional procedures are developed using as the structure of the quality management system, the context of the organization and the knowledge of the process manager. Thus the activities within each process are influenced by the quality management system. The level of influence on the process also shows the level of integration of the process in the organization's system.

At this moment, in all organizations the evaluation of the integration of processes in the quality management system is done by performing process audits using as a criterion the standard of the quality management system.

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